

ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF FIBRE REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER LOADING AND THERMAL CYCLING CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The paper investigates the shakedown and ratchetting behaviour of an idealised fiber-reinforced metal matrix composite that consists of a square array of fibers in an elastic-perfectly plastic matrix subjected to constant macro stress and thermal cycling conditions. A state-of-the-art numerical method, the Linear Matching Method (LMM), is adopted for the direct evaluation of shakedown, alternating plasticity and ratchetting behaviours of metal matrix composite in the steady cyclic state. A microscale model is considered in all analyses, which consist of continuous fibers embedded in a square matrix array. Two most common reinforcing materials alumina and silicon carbide embedded in an aluminium matrix are investigated. Various factors that affect shakedown and ratchetting behaviours of composites are analysed and discussed, including effects of fibre volume fraction and temperature on the MMC's performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) have been applied to a wide range of engineering components used in automotive, space and aircraft industries, due to their high-strength, lightweight and high-temperature capacity [1]. In order to fully utilise the potential that MMCs can give to enhanced performance components, there are significant needs for improvements and refinement in the design and modelling of composite materials. The inelastic behaviours of MMCs composed of a metallic matrix and a ceramic fibres or particles have been discussed by many researchers [2-17].

MMCs typically contain reinforced material with enhanced properties compared with the matrix material, greater stiffness and strength, lower density than the monolithic matrix material and hence are potentially advantageous for aerospace and automotive applications. However the effect of variable temperature on such materials is potentially difficult to understand. The significantly differing coefficients of thermal expansion between reinforced and matrix materials give rise to micro thermal stresses when the uniform temperature of the material is changed, having the possibility to cause low cycle fatigue (LCF) at the material interface or thermal ratchetting with relatively low mechanical load.

The strengthening effects of particles and the dependence on particle volume ratios and particle arrangement have been investigated by a number of researchers [1-7]. For MMCs, differences in the coefficient of thermal expansion of metals and ceramics result in significant thermo elastic stresses occurring on the micro scale. The effects on this strengthening of variable uniform temperature for fibre reinforced composites have also been studied [8-17] using either the experimental methods or numerical simulations. Among these numerical methods, the Linear Matching Methods (LMMs) [18] was adopted to investigate the cyclic behaviours of a particulate metal matrix composite subjected to cyclic temperature and constant stress. For the first time, a wide range design limits including the limit load, shakedown limit, and ratchet limit have been obtained comprehensively and the resulting solutions are presented as non-dimensional equations for the design purpose. However, unlike the shakedown analysis method [19], the LMM ratchet analysis method [20] adopted in [18] was still in its infancy and not able to properly evaluate the ratchet limit when the variation of temperature is

sufficiently large, due to the excessive numerical treatment in order to ensure a stable convergence. For large thermal amplitudes and small applied macro stress, there are many experimental evidences [11, 16-17] that cyclic strain growth (ratchetting) occurs. However, the LMM in [18] predicts reverse plasticity, and these solutions need to be reinvestigated.

Since then, as a direct method for generating approximate inelastic solutions and answering specific design related issues using standard finite element codes, the LMM has been much developed to evaluate the steady state cyclic behaviour of structures, including the accurate evaluation of the ratchet limit and various plastic mechanisms [21]. The associated new integrated structural analysis tool using the Linear Matching Method framework for the assessment of design limits in plasticity including load carrying capacity, shakedown limit, ratchet limit and steady state cyclic response of structures was also developed using Abaqus CAE plugins with graphical user interfaces [22, 23]. The aim of this paper is to use the new LMM shakedown and ratchet analysis methods and tool to investigate the deterioration of the apparent yield strength with variation of temperature for the fiber-reinforced metal matrix composite, and to demonstrate the ratchetting failure mechanism identified by experiments for large thermal amplitudes and small applied macro stress. Two most common reinforcing materials alumina and silicon carbide fibers embedded in an aluminium matrix are considered.

Another objective of the paper is to characterise the behaviour of the MMCs in terms of the variation of the reinforced fibre material and its volume ratio. For a structure or material including composites subjected to cyclic thermal and mechanical loads, four modes of behaviour are possible depending upon the applied load level: 1) for sufficiently low value of the applied load, the elastic stresses lie within yield leading to elastic behaviour alone; 2) the elastic stress history exceeds yield, and the plastic strains occur during the initial load cycles. The build-up of the residual stress could be such that no further plastic strain occurs after a limited number of load cycles. When this happens, the structure is said to have shakedown; 3) the applied load level exceeds the elastic shakedown limit, however no cyclic strain growth occurs but locally, in the matrix, a closed cycle of plastic strain occurs, which is known as an alternating plasticity and a potential source of fatigue initiation; 4) when the applied cyclic load exceeds the plastic shakedown limit, the matrix material experiences a cyclic growth of plastic strain, leading to an incremental plastic collapse, a situation known as ratchetting.

The evaluation of these patterns of behaviour of the MMCs may be obtained through a large number of step by step finite element calculations [24]. However, this can be difficult, very time-consuming and essentially subjective. The latest development of the LMM makes it possible to identify the primary characteristics of the region boundaries accurately and efficiently. Although the improved computational method has been applied to answer design and life assessment issues for many high temperature power plant components [23], it is a first attempt to apply the new LMM to comprehensively characterise the plastic behaviours of a continuous fibre reinforced MMC.

The LMM adopted in this paper for shakedown and ratchet analysis has been described at great length in [19, 21]. The aim of this paper is to investigate the cyclic plastic behaviour of fibre reinforced metal matrix composites under load and thermal cycling conditions using the new LMM for the shakedown and ratchet analysis. In the following section, the problem description and the detailed finite element model of the fibre reinforced MMC is provided. This is followed by the presentation of detailed limit loads, shakedown limits and ratchet limits of the fibre reinforced MMCs in section 3. The effects of different fibre materials, fibre volume fractions and temperatures on the MMC's plastic behaviours are analysed and discussed. Non-dimensional equations are derived from numerical solutions for the plastic design purpose of MMCs.

2 PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND THE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

An idealized, fiber-reinforced composite that consists of a periodic square array is taken into account to investigate the behaviour of the MMCs subjected to combined action of cyclic thermal and constant mechanical loading. The typical Abaqus FEA model is given in Fig. 1, with the detailed mesh scheme and boundary conditions. Quadrilateral plane strain elements were employed in a quarter model for all LMM shakedown and ratchet analyses. A uniaxial macro-stress σ_p is applied in a direction perpendicular to opposing faces of a generic unit cell and maintained constant. The

temperature of the composite remains uniform but varies cyclically over a range 0 to $\Delta\theta_0$ (Fig. 1-b). The FE model is subjected to homogenization boundary conditions so that the surface displacement in a single unit cell is consistent with that of adjacent identical cells within the array.

Figure 1: a) The unit cell used in the FEA; b) Applied cyclic loading.

Material property	Al	Al ₂ O ₃	S _i C
Young's modulus (E)	70 GPa	370 Gpa	450 Gpa
Thermal expansion coefficient (α)	22 MK ⁻¹	8 MK ⁻¹	4 MK ⁻¹
Yield stress σ_y	80 MPa	5 GPa	10 GPa
Poisson's ratio (ν)	0.34	0.26	0.15

Table 1: Material properties.

Two types of fiber Al₂O₃ and S_iC embedded in an elastic perfectly plastic aluminium matrix have been considered. The material properties used are presented in Table 1. The geometry of the array is defined by the fiber diameter d_f and the fiber distance $2a$. Hence the fiber volume fraction V_f can be expressed in terms of these 2 parameters as $V_f = \pi d_f^2 / 16a^2$.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Limit Analysis

The limit load, i.e. the load carrying capacity, of the MMCs subjected to the uniaxial macro-stress σ_p has been calculated using the LMM shakedown analysis as a special case. Fig. 2 shows the variation of the limit load σ_{pl} with V_f for both the Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/S_iC composites where σ_{pl} is normalised by the yield stress of aluminium material, which is equal to 80 MPa. It can be identified clearly from Fig. 2 that both alumina and silicon carbide fibres introduce the same limit load

throughout the volume range analysed. When the fibre volume fraction V_f is less than 40%, the limit loads of MMCs tend to be determined by the matrix material only. When V_f is greater than 40%, the limit loads of MMCs increase rapidly with the increase of the fibre volume fraction, where the fibre enhanced the material endurance. A linear best fit to the limit load is given by,

$$\sigma_{pl}/\sigma_y = g_1(V_f) = \begin{cases} 1.15 & 0\% < V_f < 40\% \\ 8.343V_f - 3.024 & 40\% < V_f < 65\% \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Limit tension load σ_{pl} normalised to the matrix yield stress σ_y for Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites.

3.2 Shakedown and ratchet limit

Figure 3: Shakedown and ratchet limit boundaries for the Al/Al₂O₃ composite with $V_f = 12.56\%$.

Fig. 3 shows a typical set of shakedown and ratchet limit interaction curves for the Al/Al₂O₃ composite with $V_f = 12.56\%$, where S denotes the shakedown (and elastic) region, P denotes the reverse plasticity region and R denotes the ratchetting region. The axis are expressed in non-dimensional variables, σ_p/σ_y and $\Delta\theta/\Delta\theta_0$ where $\Delta\theta_0=50^\circ\text{C}$. Two critical design limits are indicated in

Fig.3: the reverse plasticity limit $\Delta\theta_{rp}$ and ratchet limit $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$ for the MMCs subjected to the cyclic uniform temperature only. The reverse plasticity limit $\Delta\theta_{rp}$ is the maximum of the cyclic thermal load range above which reverse plasticity occurs whilst $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$ is the maximum of the cyclic thermal load range above which the structure exhibits ratchetting for any constant mechanical load and leads to an incremental plastic collapse. It is important to note that for a pure cyclic thermal load condition no ratchetting occurs even if the cyclic thermal load range is greater than $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$.

In order to further understand the mechanism and verify the obtained shakedown and ratchet limit boundaries by the LMM, six cyclic load conditions as indicated by cyclic load points A1, A2, A3, A4, A5 and A6 in Fig.3 are analysed by Abaqus step-by-step analyses. The obtained histories of plastic strain magnitude PEMAG are given in Fig. 4. It can be seen clearly from Fig. 4 that as indicated by the Fig. 3, the cyclic load point A1 within the S region exhibits a shakedown mechanism, and the cyclic load points A2 and A4 within the P region exhibit a reverse plasticity mechanism where the PEMAG fluctuates but doesn't grow. For the cyclic load points A3, A5 and A6 which are either on the ratchet limit boundary or within the R region, the plastic strain magnitude increases rapidly and indicates a strong ratchetting mechanism.

Figure 4: History of plastic strain magnitude for the cyclic load point A1, A2, A3, A4, A5 and A6, defined in Fig. 2 and evaluated by a set of step-by-step analysis.

Figure 5: Contours of effective ratchetting strain for the cyclic load points A3 and A6, and plastic strain range for the cyclic load points A2 and A4, for the Al/Al₂O₃ composite with $V_f=12.56\%$.

Contours of effective ratchet strain $\bar{\epsilon}_{\text{RTC}}^{\text{p}}$ for the cyclic load points A3 and A6 in ratchetting region and the plastic strain range $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^{\text{p}}$ for the points A2 and A4 within the reverse plasticity region are also shown in Fig. 5. It can be observed that the ratchetting mechanism owing to a high thermal load and a small mechanical load (point A3) is different from that with a smaller thermal load and higher mechanical load (point A6) in terms of effective ratchetting strain. For the cyclic load points A2 and A4, the composite exhibits a local reverse plasticity mechanism which may leads to a low cycle fatigue failure. However due to the larger constant mechanical load, the cyclic load point A4 produces slightly larger plastic strain range around the interface comparing with the cyclic load point A2.

Figure 6: Comparison of reverse plasticity limit $\Delta\theta_{rp}$ between the composites Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC.

Figure 7: Comparison of ratchet limit $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$ between the composites Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC.

Figs. 6 and 7 present the magnitudes of the reverse plasticity limit $\Delta\theta_{rp}$ and ratchet limit $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$ for the entire range of fibre volume fraction V_f for both the Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites. It can be observed that the variation of the reverse plasticity limit $\Delta\theta_{rp}$ with V_f shown in Fig. 6 exhibits the same trend but with slightly different magnitudes between the two fibers whilst the variation of ratchet limit $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$ shown in Fig. 7 remain almost the same.

It can also be noticed from Fig.6 that the reverse plasticity limit $\Delta\theta_{rp}$ tends to remain stable until 40% of the volume fraction even if it decreases with the volume fraction when $V_f > 40\%$. Fig.7 shows that the ratchet limit $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$ remains constant for the smaller fibre volume fraction ($V_f < 20\%$) and the larger fibre volume fraction ($V_f > 40\%$), but with a reduction in the magnitude when V_f increases from 20% to 40%. It is worth noting that the reverse plasticity limit $\Delta\theta_{rp}$ is determined by the local maximum thermal stress range at the material interface due to the significant difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion between fibre and matrix materials. For the ratchet limit $\Delta\theta_{rtc}$, the local thermal stress caused by the material mismatch does not have significant effect. The ratchet limit

is governed by a global failure mechanism, which is mainly determined by the combined action of the constant mechanical load and the affected area of the thermal stress on the matrix material. Only when the fibre volume fraction is large enough, the local cyclic thermal stress due to the material mismatch starts to play an important role as the effect of the thermal stress becomes global mechanism.

A linear fit to both the reverse plastic limit and ratchet limit is given by equations (2) and (3) respectively;

$$\Delta\theta_{rp}/\Delta\theta_0 = g_2(V_f) = \begin{cases} 1.47 & 0\% < V_f < 40\% \\ -1.246V_f + 1.968 & 40\% < V_f < 65\% \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta\theta_{rtc}/\Delta\theta_0 = g_3(V_f) = \begin{cases} 2.25 & 0\% < V_f < 20\% \\ -2.234V_f + 2.688 & 20\% < V_f < 40\% \\ 1.83 & 40\% < V_f < 65\% \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

3.3 Plastic Strain Range and Ratchetting Strain

Figure 8: Maximum plastic strain ranges and ratchetting strains per cycle of the Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites subjected to a wide range of varying cyclic thermal loads $\Delta\theta$ and constant $\sigma_p=0\text{MPa}$ ($V_f=12.56\%$).

Figure 9: Maximum plastic strain ranges and ratchetting strains per cycle of the Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites subjected to a wide range of varying cyclic thermal loads $\Delta\theta$ and constant $\sigma_p=20\text{MPa}$ ($V_f=12.56\%$).

Figs. 8 and 9 present the calculated maximum von Mises plastic strain range $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_{\max}^p$ and ratchetting strain per cycle $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_{\text{RTC}}^p$ by the LMM for both the composite Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC ($V_f=12.56\%$) subjected to varying cyclic thermal loads $\Delta\theta$ and constant $\sigma_p=0$ and 20.5MPa, respectively. It can be identified that the magnitude of the $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_{\max}^p$ and $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_{\text{RTC}}^p$ for each cyclic temperature range is higher for the composite Al/SiC than Al/Al₂O₃. All these plastic strain range and ratchetting strain solutions have been verified by the Abaqus step-by-step analysis, which produces nearly identical results comparing with the LMM, with an error less than 1%.

The coincidence of the LMM and Abaqus step-by-step analysis results in Figs. 8 and 9 confirms the accuracy of the LMM. However, comparing with the LMM, the Abaqus step-by-step analysis involves much more significant computer effort to produce the same results. It is also observed that there is no ratchetting for any cyclic thermal loads when the uniaxial macro stress $\sigma_p=0$. However, when $\sigma_p=20\text{MPa}$, the ratchetting strain occurs when the cyclic uniform temperature range $\Delta\theta/\Delta\theta_0$ is greater than ratchet limit, which equals to 2 according to the interaction diagram (Fig. 3) for $V_f=12.56\%$. The most interesting observation from Figs. 8 and 9 is that the magnitude of maximum plastic strain range concerning the fatigue crack initiation not only depends upon the varying cyclic thermal loads $\Delta\theta$, but is also affected by the constant uniaxial macro-stress σ_p . The mild increase of the plastic strain range due to the existence of the constant uniaxial macro-stress agrees very well with the general experimental observations.

Although the maximum von Mises plastic strain ranges are different for the composites Al/SiC and Al/Al₂O₃ subjected to the pure cyclic thermal loads as shown in Fig. 8, a unified plot of the maximum plastic strain range for both composites can be presented in Fig. 10 in terms of the ratio $\Delta\sigma^\theta/\Delta\sigma_{rp}^\theta$, where $\Delta\sigma^\theta$ denotes the maximum effective elastic thermal stress corresponding to a temperature change $\Delta\theta$ whilst $\Delta\sigma_{rp}^\theta$ is a fixed value and it is equal to twice the yield stress of the matrix σ_y .

Figure 10: Unified maximum plastic strain ranges $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}_{\max}^p$ for the low cycle fatigue assessment of both the Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites subjected to a wide range of varying cyclic thermal loads for $V_f=12.56\%$.

It can be observed clear from Fig. 10 that for both the fibers, the plastic strain range occurs when the maximum elastic thermal stress range $\Delta\sigma^\theta$ is greater than $2\sigma_y$. For the same temperature range $\Delta\theta$, the maximum elastic thermal stress range $\Delta\sigma^\theta$ would be different for the composites Al/SiC and Al/Al₂O₃ due to the different coefficients of thermal expansion of fibre materials. The calculated maximum plastic strain range can be represented by a unified linear fitting solution as shown in Fig.10, where the ratio $\Delta\sigma^\theta/\Delta\sigma_{rp}^\theta$ is a function of the applied cyclic temperature range $\Delta\theta$:

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma^\theta}{\Delta\sigma_{rp}^\theta} = \frac{\Delta\theta}{\Delta\theta_{ref}} \quad (4)$$

where the reference temperature $\Delta\theta_{ref}$ is equal to either $\Delta\theta_{Al_2O_3}=74.68^\circ\text{C}$ for the composite Al/Al₂O₃ or $\Delta\theta_{SiC}=64.85^\circ\text{C}$ for the composite Al/SiC.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Using the powerful LMM and software tool, this paper investigated the effects of different fibre materials, fibre volume fractions and the applied cyclic temperature load and constant mechanical load on the MMC's plastic behaviours including the shakedown, reverse plasticity and ratchetting behaviours. The proposed microscale model of an idealised fiber-reinforced metal matrix composite that consists of a square array of alumina or silicon carbide fibers in an elastic-perfectly plastic aluminium matrix subjected to constant macro stress and thermal cycling conditions provides an efficient way to investigate the material mismatch behaviour and how reinforced fibre material with enhanced properties affects the mechanical performance of MMCs. It has been demonstrated in this paper that when the fibre volume fraction is greater than 40%, the further increase of the fibre volume fraction will increase the load carrying capacity of the MMCs. However it will slightly reduce the maximum of the cyclic thermal load range above which reverse plasticity occurs, as well as the maximum of the cyclic thermal load range above which the structure exhibits ratchetting for any constant mechanical load.

In addition, both the plastic strain ranges and ratchetting strains of the Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites subjected to a wide range of cyclic uniform temperatures have been calculated, and a unified formula of evaluating the maximum plastic strain ranges for the low cycle fatigue assessment purpose of both the Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/SiC composites has been proposed. The mild increase of the plastic strain range due to the existence of the constant uniaxial macro-stress has also been verified. The obtained ratchet limit interaction curves by the LMM in this paper demonstrated the ratchetting failure mechanism for large thermal amplitudes and small applied macro stress, which agrees very well with the general experimental observations.

A set of step-by-step analyses were carried out in order to provide a validation of the LMM's results in terms of both accuracy and CPU time consumption. All the calculations presented in this paper demonstrate that it is possible to efficiently characterise the cyclic plastic behaviour of MMCs by using the Linear Matching Method.

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